

GROWTH PERFORMANCE, PROXIMATE AND MINERAL ASSAY OF PLEUROTUS TUBER-REGIUM (FR.) SING MUSHROOM GROWN IN IMO STATE POLYTECHNIC FARMLAND SUPPLEMENTED WITH PIG AND POULTRY DUNGS

Onwubuche B.C.^a,

Nwinee S.A.^b,

Adumanya O.C.U.^c,

Umensofor G.A.^d,

^aDepartment of Science Laboratory Tech.

Imo State Polytechnic,

Umuagwo, Imo State

^bDepartment of Science Laboratory Tech.

Petroleum Training Institute, Effurun, Delta State, Nigeria

^cBiochemistry Unit,

Imo State Polytechnic, Umuagwo-Ohaji, Nigeria

^dDepartment of Agriculture

Imo State Local Government Civil Service Commission., Nigeria

Abstract

The cultivation of *Pleurotus tuber regium* in an open farmland are rarely common, hence this pilot study assayed the growth performance, proximate and mineral assay of *Pleurotus tuber-regium* (Fr.) Sing mushroom grown using its sclerotia in Imo State Polytechnic farmland supplemented with pig and poultry(birds) dungs. The results (Figure 1 and Table 1) indicated that the pig (A) and poultry (B) dungs supported the growth more favourably than the farmland (C) alone with comparable nutritional values. While the Table 2 showed that the mushrooms from this pilot study were rich in mineral contents. The results from this study underscored that the Polytechnic farmland as well as its pig and poultry dungs supplemented, supported favourable growth and yield with appreciable nutritional values.

Keywords: *Mushroom, dung, growth, yield, supplement*